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Material Limitations and Processing Challenges of Bio-Based Thermoplastics: A Review

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ABSTRACT

The increasing production and consumption of petro-based plastics raise significant environmental concerns due to their persistence and accumulation in ecosystems. Biopolymers, derived from renewable sources such as plants and microorganisms, offer a sustainable alternative to traditional plastics. These materials are moldable and recyclable through thermal processes, providing versatility for various industrial applications, such as commercial thermoplastic materials. This review provides a comprehensive overview of biopolymeric thermoplastics (b-bTPs), discussing their compositions, challenges, and recent advances. Key topics include the formulation of b-bTPs using additives and blends to improve their properties, the application of advanced techniques such as microcellular injection molding, the recyclability of b-bTPs foam parts, and future trends and prospects. This analysis highlights the potential of b-bTPs to replace conventional plastics in numerous applications, contributing to a more sustainable industry.

1 | Introduction

In recent decades, the production and consumption of plastics have grown exponentially due to their versatility, durability, and low cost, leading to a global environmental crisis. In 2022, global plastics production exceeded 400 million metric tonnes. Although “plastics” is a broad term encompassing thermoplastics, thermosets, and elastomers, the vast majority of this production consists of fossil-based thermoplastics, widely used in packaging and consumer goods [1].

Plastics, though with numerous advantages to their use, the high durability, result in problematic environmental persistence, as most traditional plastics are not biodegradable and can take hundreds of years to disintegrate [2]. Today, the manufacture of plastics is a synthetic-based process that involves energy- and resource-intensive steps (from extracting and refining fossil fuels such as oil or natural gas to the raw materials used), to polymerize monomers such as ethylene, propylene, and styrene. This constant use of raw

materials is resulting in a scarcity of resources that presents a problem to the plastics community. This combined with the known problems associated with the disintegration process of plastics (which can result in the formation of microplastics, posing health risks to both animals and humans) and a consumeristic society results in around 40% of plastics produced products being discarded after a single use [3], swiftly increasing pollution in oceans, soil, and even the food chain, with adverse consequences for health and the environment. Furthermore, the burning of plastic waste, a fundamental disposal practice, aggravates environmental pollution as it releases harmful substances and is responsible for around 4.5% of global GHG (greenhouse gas emissions) [4]. Still, the worldwide production of thermoplastics is projected to increase considerably from 2025 to 2050, reaching around 590 million metric tons [5]. This dependency also poses economic risks, as fossil fuel markets are subject to geopolitical instabilities and price fluctuations.

Consequently, the exploration of alternatives has become imperative, and important organizations, such as the European Union,

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have already started to pressure this modification in plastic production, which, in 2022, has issued a mandatory requirement that 30%–55% of a thermoplastic component has to be of recycled or bio-based content by 2030 [6]. All evidence suggests b-bTPs as a viable alternative for synthetic-based plastics. B-bTPs can be defined as thermoplastics partially or totally derived from renewable resources. However, this definition is considered ambiguous and without precision, as currently there is no mandatory minimum bio-based content or certification that regulates this definition/product labelling. To regulate the bio-based market, the European Technical Committee for Standardization developed the standard CEN/TC411 directed to bio-based products that offer guidance on measuring methods for bio-based content; nevertheless, the application of this standard is not mandatory [7].

Another sustainable approach under consideration is the incorporation of recycled materials into plastic products. However, the origin of these materials imposes significant limitations on their application, especially in food packaging, where contaminants present in the recycled plastic may migrate to the surface and come into contact with food. Additionally, monitoring all potential contaminants is both expensive and time consuming. In this context, bio-based thermoplastics (b-bTPs), which are partially or entirely derived from renewable sources, have emerged as a promising alternative. Beyond their renewable origin, some b-bTPs also offer added environmental advantages, such as lower carbon footprints over their life cycles and, in certain cases, enhanced biodegradability.

Despite their potential, the substitution of fossil-based thermoplastics with b-bTPs still faces substantial challenges. These include limitations in thermal and mechanical properties (such as thermal sensitivity, low resistance to shear rates, and narrow processing windows), as well as difficulties integrating them into existing industrial processes. Moreover, the limited availability of biological raw materials restricts large-scale production, making it difficult to meet the increasing demand for sustainable alternatives. Addressing these challenges requires not only advances in polymer developments but also the development of innovative processing technologies tailored to bio-based feedstocks.

Therefore, it is essential to deepen our understanding of b-bTPs, particularly in relation to key stages of their processing, including compounding, injection molding, and recycling. This review integrates recent quantitative data, highlights regional market dynamics, evaluates environmental impacts, and identifies unresolved challenges such as phase compatibility, limited recycling cycles, and feedstock variability. The scope of this review is limited to thermoplastics that are partially or fully derived from renewable sources, excluding thermosets and non-biobased alternatives.

2 | Biopolymers and Bio-Based Thermoplastics (b-bTPs)

2.1 | Classification

Although the term bioplastic is often used broadly, it is important to distinguish between bio-based, biodegradable, and compostable materials. Not all bio-based polymers are biodegradable (e.g., bio-PE or bio-PET), and not all biodegradable plastics are

derived from renewable feedstocks (e.g., PBAT). This distinction is critical to avoid confusion in markets, policy, and legislation. Challenges involve clearly defining the conditions under which biodegradation can occur, whether in soil, aquatic environments, or in industrial or home composting. They also include the need for effective composting infrastructure and waste management systems, as well as transparent communication with consumers to prevent misunderstandings or misleading claims (“greenwashing”). Finally, the harmonization of standards and legislation across different countries and regions remains a key requirement for the broader adoption of these materials. International standards such as ASTM D6400, EN 13432, and ISO 17088 define specific criteria for biodegradability and compostability, including minimum biodegradation rates under controlled conditions, physical disintegration, absence of ecotoxic effects, and limits on heavy metals. However, adoption remains uneven and largely dependent on national regulations, industrial composting infrastructure, and market demand [8]. Recent literature confirms these distinctions and emphasizes that the sustainability potential of bioplastics depends as much on their chemical structure and end-of-life conditions as on their renewable origin [9].

Biopolymers are materials derived from natural sources or synthesized from monomers. These monomers can be obtained either directly from renewable biomass (e.g., sugars, starch, cellulose) or produced via chemical synthesis using bio-based feedstocks (e.g., fermentation-derived lactic acid for PLA). Thus, biopolymers may originate from natural extraction or from synthetic routes using renewable raw materials. Sourced from renewable resources, when combined with the right additives, biopolymers have the advantage of being moldable and recyclable through thermal processes. This characteristic significantly reduces waste and dependence on non-renewable resources associated with production.

In addition, many b-bTPs are biodegradable, accelerating their decomposition and mitigating long-term pollution problems [10]. However, it is important to distinguish between biobased and biodegradable materials. A polymer can be biobased (derived from renewable sources) but not biodegradable (e.g., bio-PE), or biodegradable but fossil-based (e.g., PBAT). According to Van Den Oever et al. [11], the term bioplastic refers either to the bio-based origin (biopolymer) or the biodegradable nature of a plastic. For clarity, this review focuses specifically on biobased thermoplastics, i.e., thermoplastics that are partially or fully derived from renewable sources, regardless of their biodegradability. Biobased thermoplastics can also be classified based on the proportion of renewable content. Fully biobased thermoplastics are made entirely from renewable feedstocks, whereas partially biobased materials include both renewable and fossil-derived components. This distinction is critical for assessing environmental benefits, regulatory compliance, and lifecycle performance. Biopolymers thus not only offer renewable feedstocks but also support circular economy principles, enabling closed-loop material cycles when combined with appropriate recycling or composting processes.

Furthermore, the biopolymers may also be classified according to their origin, as shown in Figure 1. Plant-derived

FIGURE 1 | Types of biopolymers according to their source. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/app.70436)]

polymers include starches, cellulose, and lignin, whereas animal sources provide proteins such as gelatin and casein. Microorganisms can produce polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) and other fermentation-based polymers. Algae represent an emerging source for polysaccharides and bio-based plastics, and synthetic routes utilize bio-based monomers produced via chemical synthesis from renewable feedstocks. This classification highlights the diverse origins of biopolymers and their potential for tailored applications depending on source and processing method.

Therefore, the literature already presents a wide range of options with the most common being.

2.1.1 | Polylactide Acid

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) is one of the most widely used b-bTTPs, commonly found in packaging, disposable cutlery, and 3D printing applications [12–15]. PLA is produced through the fermentation of renewable sources such as corn, cassava, sugar beets, and sugar cane. During this process, sugars are converted into lactic acid, which subsequently undergoes polymerization to form PLA.

PLA is a lightweight material with a lower density compared to conventional thermoplastics like PET, enabling the production of lighter products. This property contributes to material

savings and potential environmental benefits [16, 17]. However, PLA recycling requires specialized infrastructure, which is uncommon and costly to implement.

2.1.2 | Polyhydroxyalkanoates

Polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) may be used to produce organic substrates through the fermentation of microorganisms. PHAs are a family of polymers with physical properties that may vary from rigid and brittle to flexible and elastic materials, depending on their specific composition. They are fully biodegradable and compostable, offering potential applications in packaging, medical implants, and agricultural materials [18]. Due to their tunable mechanical properties and biodegradability, PHAs are particularly attractive for high-value applications.

2.1.3 | Starch Thermoplastic

Thermoplastic starch (TPS) is derived from plant starches such as corn, potatoes, or wheat. This b-bTTPs is treated with plasticizers such as glycerol to break down the intermolecular bonds, allowing for its processability. TPS is biodegradable and can be blended with other polymers to enhance its mechanical and barrier properties. It is commonly applied in plastic films, packaging, and short-lived products [19].

However, TPS is highly sensitive to moisture, which limits its applications. Therefore, blending is essential for performance improvement.

2.1.4 | Polybutylene Succinate

Polybutylene succinate (PBS) is a biodegradable aliphatic polyester synthesized from succinate and butanediol. PBS has properties similar to polyethylene (PE) and polypropylene (PP) but is obtained from renewable sources. Applications include films for packaging, single-use items, and agricultural uses. PBS can substitute PE or PP in certain applications, offering similar mechanical performance while providing biodegradability and renewable sourcing. Additionally, the low density of PBS contributes to reduce the overall weight of the products, benefiting both logistics and the environment [20].

2.1.5 | Other Examples

Other examples include Polyethylene Furoate (PEF), which is similar to PET but derived from plant-based sugars, showing promise as an alternative for bottles and beverage packaging [21]. Bio-based polyethylene (Bio-PE), derived from sugarcane ethanol, mimics traditional PE and is used in packaging, bottles, and films [22]. Bio-PP, derived from sugarcane, shares similar to PP and can be used in applications ranging from packaging to car components [23]. Polyglycolic Acid (PGA), in turn, excels in medical applications such as sutures and tissue support due to its biodegradability [24]. Polyhydroxy urethanes (PHUs) possess biodegradable and biocompatible properties, suitable for biomedical devices, drug delivery, and tissue engineering [25]. Another example is Bio-PET, derived, for example, from sugarcane, which is used in packaging,

textiles, and fibers, broadening a range of sustainable plastic options [26].

Companies such as Nature Works [27], BASF [28], Corbion [29] and Novamont [30] are key players in the bioplastic market through significant investments in research and development, enhancing the properties and expanding the applications of their products.

According to IDTechEx, PLA leads in technological maturity (TRL), though recycling infrastructure is limited and costly [31]. Emerging bio-based polymers, such as PEF and PHUs, are attracting increasing industrial interest, with potential applications ranging from packaging to biomedical fields. However, their technological readiness varies (Figure 2), leading producers to often favor more conventional polymers. Despite their benefits, b-bTPs still demand a strong commitment to cost-effectiveness to achieve broader adoption.

2.2 | Properties of Biobased Thermoplastics

One of the key technical challenges of bio-based thermoplastics (b-bTPs) is their narrow processing window. For instance, PLA is prone to degradation under high shear conditions, TPS is extremely sensitive to moisture, and PHAs can undergo thermal breakdown. These limitations often necessitate the use of stabilizers or the optimization of extrusion and injection molding parameters. From a mechanical perspective, many b-bTPs are brittle and exhibit low impact resistance, which restricts their application in flexible packaging and structural components. Barrier performance is also a concern, as elevated gas and water vapor permeability can compromise the shelf life of food and pharmaceutical products. Studies by Negrete-Bolagay et al. [32] and Beukelaar et al. [33] further emphasize the need to address

FIGURE 2 | TRL levels. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

these processing, mechanical, and barrier-related constraints to broaden the industrial applicability of b-bTPs.

B-bTPs exhibit a wide variety of properties depending on their chemical composition, source, and degree of processing. Their performance characteristics can differ significantly from conventional fossil-based thermoplastics, which directly affects their suitability for specific applications. A comprehensive understanding of their mechanical, thermal, barrier, rheological, and biodegradation properties is essential for industrial implementation. These characteristics are often influenced by the molecular structure, crystallinity, moisture sensitivity and thermal behavior of the base biopolymer.

Mechanically, b-bTPs generally show lower performance compared to traditional thermoplastics, which remains one of the main barriers to their wider adoption. Typically, limitations include lower tensile strength, reduced stiffness, and increased brittleness, which restrict its applicability in load-bearing or high-performance contexts. For example, PLA, despite its popularity, is naturally fragile and susceptible to crack propagation, limiting its use in flexible packaging or impact-prone applications.

Thermal properties are another challenge associated with b-bTPs. Many of these materials have lower thermal stability and softening temperatures compared to their petrochemical counterparts. For example, PLA has a relatively low glass transition temperature (around 60°C), which can lead to deformation under heat, making it unsuitable for high-temperature applications such as hot food packaging. The crystal structure of certain b-bTPs, such as PBS or PHAs, offers higher thermal resistance compared to amorphous bioplastics, but the thermal behavior remains limited for specific applications.

Regarding barrier properties, such as water vapor transmission rate (WVTR) and oxygen permeability, it should be noted that b-bTPs generally have higher gas and moisture permeability, especially in the case of TPS, which is highly hygroscopic, which limits applications such as food packaging and pharmaceuticals where shelf life and performance in humid or oxygen-sensitive environments are critical factors. In addition, b-bTPs generally have greater sensitivity to viscosity, temperature and shear rate, which can potentiate problems in the processing techniques used such as extrusion and injection molding.

On the other hand, a great advantage of b-bTPs is their biodegradability and potential for composting, whether industrial or even domestic. Materials such as PLA, PBS, and PHAs can break down into natural compounds, reducing environmental persistence. However, biodegradation rates depend on polymer type, product geometry, environmental conditions (temperature, humidity, microbial activity), and additives. Life cycle assessments indicate that environmental benefits of b-bTPs rely not only on their biodegradability but also on sustainable feedstock sourcing and energy-efficient processing.

Thus, understanding these properties is critical to guide material selection, compounding strategies, and processing methods to maximize performance while ensuring sustainability. Figure 3 presents a SWOT analysis of b-bTPs, summarizing their key

strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats, including aspects such as renewable sourcing, potential biodegradability, processing challenges, and market limitations.

3 | Compounding of b-bTPs

Recent strategies have aimed to overcome the inherent limitations of biopolymers. Chain extenders and crosslinkers have been shown to enhance molecular weight and rheological stability, improving PLA and PBAT processability [34]. Reinforcements such as nanocellulose, nanoclays, and biochar enhance mechanical strength, stiffness, and barrier properties while maintaining renewable origin [35]. Additionally, blends like PLA + PHA, PLA + TPS, and PBAT+TPS provide a practical balance between rigidity and flexibility, reduce production costs, and expand potential applications [32].

Due to their intrinsic limitations in mechanical and thermal performance, bio-based thermoplastics often require the strategic use of additives and blending during compounding to achieve properties suitable for industrial applications. In general, bioplastics tend to exhibit inferior mechanical properties, such as lower tensile strength and stiffness, and they often lack the thermal stability required for certain applications, such as food packing for preservation [36]. The production cost of bioplastics remains relatively high due to the limited availability of raw material and a lack of market interest, coupled with associated costs. In addition to production costs, these raw materials are difficult to process, and, their high sensitivity to humidity may lead to water absorption, which may cause degradation of the material through hydrolysis during compounding. These factors collectively limit the applicability of b-bTPs. To address these challenges, strategic additive incorporation is critical [37].

Blending different biopolymers can combine the advantages of each component. For instance, PLA + PHA improves flexibility and impact resistance while maintaining biodegradability; PLA + TPS enhances processability and mechanical properties, as TPS acts as a natural plasticizer; PBS + PBAT yields improved mechanical performance and biodegradability, suitable for packaging films and compostable bags [38]. Such blending strategies are essential for aligning b-bTPs properties with industrial performance requirements, particularly for applications that demand specific mechanical or thermal behavior.

Among the available additives, chemical or physical foaming agents [39], nucleating agents [40–42], compatibilizers [43–45], and other property modifiers play key roles. These additives serve multiple functions, ranging from mechanical strength and thermal stability to improving processability and promoting the aesthetics of the final product.

In this section, we delve into a comprehensive review of the additive strategies employed to enhance the performance and properties of bio-based thermoplastics. Through an in-depth analysis of the mechanisms behind various additives, along with insights from recent advancements and innovations in the field, we aim to provide a nuanced understanding of the additive landscape of bioplastics. Specifically, we will explore the role of chemical and physical foaming agents in facilitating foaming processes, which

FIGURE 3 | SWOT analysis of b-bTPs in the context of material properties. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/app.70456)]

reduce material density and impart insulation properties [46, 47]. In addition, we will examine the role of nucleating agents in promoting crystallization kinetics, thereby enhancing mechanical strength and dimensional stability [48–50]. Compatibilizers will also be analyzed for their ability to improve interfacial adhesion between bioplastics and other materials, enabling the development of high-performance blends and composites [41, 51, 52]. By leveraging the synergistic effects of additives, bioplastics can achieve performance levels closer to conventional plastics, supporting their broader adoption across industries.

3.1 | Chemical Foaming Agents and Physical Foaming Agents

Foaming agents are substances that, when introduced into the injection molding process, decompose or vaporize easily at certain temperatures, producing large volumes of gases or vapors that enable the formation of structures with cells (foams). The resulting foamed structures can significantly reduce weight and material usage, contributing to both performance and sustainability of products.

There are two main types of foaming agents: Chemical Foaming Agents (CFA) and Physical Foaming Agents (PFA).

PFA are generally in liquid or gaseous state and, due to the high temperatures and shear rates of the injection molding process,

form a homogeneous solution of an inert gas such as nitrogen or carbon dioxide within the polymer.

As a general rule, CFAs are solid, organic, or inorganic additives mixed with the molten polymer. During processing, the CFA undergoes a chemical transformation releasing gas through decomposition within a defined temperature range. These gases remain in the supercritical fluid (SCF) phase until a high-pressure drop occurs, resulting in gas (N_2 or CO_2) expansion. During the decomposition of the CFA, by-products are formed, in part, due to the chemical reactions with the polymer chemical structure. The decomposition process can be categorized into two reactions: exothermic or endothermic [53]. In the presence of exothermic CFAs, energy is released during the decomposition, increasing the temperature of the polymer beyond the initial setting. It is therefore crucial to adjust the temperature profile to avoid potential material degradation. Endothermic agents, in contrast, require a constant energy supply to sustain the reaction, resulting in a more controlled decomposition process. In both cases, the expansion reaction results in the formation of low molecular weight compounds [54].

In both cases, the gas in the SCF phase forms a single-phase mixture with the molten polymer. With the pressure drop in the mold, gas diffusion and nucleation occur, which expand until the polymer cools and solidifies, creating voids in the polymer matrix. This automatically generates a high degree of supersaturation,

TABLE 1 | Advantages and disadvantages.

CFA		PFA	
Advantages	Disadvantages	Advantages	Disadvantages
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Lower initial cost [54]. – Conventional injection molding machine [54]. – Simplicity of the process [54]. – Versatile application [54, 57]. – Wide availability and variety of agents [57]. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Possible release of toxic by-products that influence properties (e.g., discoloration) [54]. – Require corrosion-resistant materials in the injection unit [54]. – Heterogeneous cell structure: cells of greater dimension and variability [57]. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Lower operating costs in the long run [54]. – More stable process [54]. – Cellular structure is more uniform [58]. – Used for applications that cannot suffer significant loss of mechanical properties [58]. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Requires process fine-tuning/complex stabilization [54]. – Flammability risks associated with gases [54]. – Higher initial cost due to specialized equipment [54]. – It requires adaptation of the screw to inject gas [58].

converting dispersed gas molecules into gas bubbles (voids), creating a closed-cell cellular structure [54]. Moreover, the presence of gas in the polymer reduces the material viscosity due to the fluidic behavior of the SCF, thus enabling the polymer to be processed at lower temperatures and pressures. This is particularly advantageous for bioplastics, which, due to their thermally sensitive nature, need to be processed within a narrow temperature range.

While the CFAs can be used in conventional injection molding equipment, PFAs require a specific equipment modification but offer key advantages, including a wider processing temperatures range and absence of by-product formation [55, 56]. The choice between CFA and PFA depends on the desired foam properties, equipment availability, and sensitivity of the b-bTPs being processed. Table 1 summarizes the main advantages and disadvantages of each foaming agent.

3.2 | Nucleating Agents

Nucleating agents are functional additives used to promote the formation of nucleation sites within the polymer matrix. These additives facilitate the generation of small, uniformly distributed gas bubbles, thereby contributing to an improved cellular structure in polymer foams. By increasing the density of nucleation sites, these agents enable better control over cell size and distribution, resulting in thinner cellular morphologies and enhanced mechanical properties [59]. Nucleation is particularly important in b-bTPs, where controlled crystallization can mitigate issues of brittleness and dimensional instability.

Martin Borůvka et al. [60] demonstrated that nucleating agents derived from cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) and lignin-coated cellulose nanocrystals (L-CNCs) significantly increase nucleation density, enhance crystallization kinetics, and improve thermal stability in b-bTPs like PLA. Similarly, although not bio-based, Maiz et al. [61] investigated a specific nucleating agent that markedly improves the mechanical properties of thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) when subjected to cooling below a critical threshold rate. The insights from this study may be transferable to bio-based systems with similar morphological

behavior or crystallization challenges. While TPU is not within the scope of bio-based materials, the insights from this study may be transferable to bio-based systems with analogous morphological or crystallization behavior.

Kang et al. [62] investigated the effect of chemically modified thermoplastic starch (CMPS) on the thermal properties and isothermal crystallization kinetics of PLA, employing differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Their study revealed that the presence of a nucleating agent in PLA led to enhanced crystallization, which in turn affects its melting temperature. Although the performance of CMPS as a nucleating agent was comparable to granular starch, it was slightly inferior to talc. Nevertheless, CMPS presents a fully biodegradable alternative, offering a residue-free nucleating agent suitable for biobased and biodegradable polymers.

3.3 | Compatibilizers

Compatibilizers are additives that enhance the compatibility between distinct polymeric phases, crucial for achieving excellent properties in otherwise incompatible polymer blends. Miscibility refers to the behavior in a mixture, determining the number and composition of phases that are formed in a mixture. Polymer blends may be categorized as: (1) completely miscible, (2) partially miscible, and (3) fully immiscible [63]. Proper compatibilization is especially relevant for b-bTPs, which often involve blending polymers of diverse origin and polarity.

The miscibility of a polymer blend may be assessed through its morphology (homogeneous or heterogeneous) and the glass transition temperature (T_g). A completely miscible blend exhibits a homogeneous morphology with a single T_g, located between the T_g values of the individual components. In contrast, a fully immiscible blend typically shows a separate macro phase morphology, characterized by a coarse interface, large dispersed domains, poor phase adhesion, and two distinct T_g values. A partially miscible blend consists of two phases, each homogeneous with one polymer partially dissolved in the other, exhibiting two T_g values that vary between those of the components

[64]. Compatibilizers therefore play a crucial role in achieving homogeneous properties and enhancing the structural integrity of polymer blends.

In this sense, compatibilizers improve adhesion between the polymer matrix and any additives or reinforcements, thereby stabilizing the structure. The addition of compatibilizers leads to enhanced mechanical properties and durability in the final product, along with better dispersion. This is achieved by reducing the size of the dispersed phase through lower interfacial tension and by preventing coalescence, stabilizing the morphology [65]. Well-chosen compatibilizers enable b-BTPs blends to approach the performance of conventional plastics.

Fredi et al. [38] outlined three compatibilization methods: (I) non-reactive compatibilization using block- and graft-copolymers; (II) reactive compatibilization, in which the copolymer is formed in situ during processing; and (III) compatibilization induced by nano- or micro-fillers. Examples of compatibilizers use are documented in the literature. D'Anna et al. [66], for instance, demonstrated that compatibilizers such as ethylene oxide/propylene oxide block copolymers and liquid surfactants effectively improve the miscibility of polylactic acid and poly-hydroxy butyrate, leading to enhanced morphology, crystallinity, and elastic modulus values. Oyama et al. [67] found that biodegradable compatibilizers, such as microbially derived poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyhexanoate) and poly(ϵ -caprolactone), can improve the toughness of PHA materials without compromising biodegradability.

3.4 | Properties Modifiers

Properties modifiers are additives designed to improve specific material properties, such as strength, flexibility, thermal stability, or barrier performance. Examples include plasticizers that increase flexibility and reduce brittleness; reinforcements such as glass or natural fibers to improve mechanical resistance; flame retardants to improve fire resistance; and antioxidants to extend the end-of-life and enhance thermal stability [68].

Fahrngruber et al. [69] highlighted how potato-fiber modified thermoplastic starch increases rigidity and mechanical stiffness, while also modifying sorption characteristics, making it a useful additive for customized packaging materials. Zhejing Cai et al. [70] showed that incorporating epoxidized natural rubber (ENR) and natural rubber (NR) as modifiers in thermoplastic potato starch (TPS) can improve mechanical and thermal properties, water absorption, and biodegradability. Kai Xu et al. [71] also discovered that adding alkali-treated kapok fiber (MKF) and high-efficiency flame retardant (NTPA) into the PLA matrix enhances the flame retardancy and toughness of the biodegradable thermoplastic.

4 | Foamed Parts Production Technologies With b-BTPs

b-BTPs can be processed using conventional polymer conversion techniques. However, their specific thermal behavior, viscosity, and sensitivity to degradation often require optimized conditions or modifications in standard processing methods.

Foaming technologies are widely used to reduce material density while maintaining mechanical strength, providing solutions for packaging, insulation, and lightweight components. The choice of foaming technology is influenced by the origin of the biopolymer, feedstock characteristics, and the technological maturity of the process. Several studies demonstrate the feasibility and advantages of these technologies, providing practical justification for their current TRL levels. For example, foam injection molding (FIM) of PLA or PBS considered at TRL 7–8 [72], indicating industrial readiness, whereas foamed 3D printing of PHAs is currently at TRL 4–5 [73], reflecting ongoing experimental development. This section presents key technologies for producing foamed components using b-BTPs and discusses their associated challenges, advantages, and relevant literature examples.

4.1 | FIM Process

FIM technology emerged in 1960 through the combination of compounds that can be thermally expanded (foaming agents). This technology is used to facilitate the creation of foam in the structure of components, which can absorb sound, have low thermal conductivity, and are resistant to shrinkage and warping. Therefore, foaming technology is commonly used for weight reduction, for example, in protective packaging [74] and thermal and acoustic insulation [75], because its cellular structure significantly reduces the density of the material while maintaining good mechanical strength and impact properties [76].

To achieve these properties, a set of steps is followed, starting with the introduction of a foaming agent into the melt during the injection molding process [56]. The CFAs are introduced directly into the hopper along with the plastic granule, as for the PFAs, the injection molding barrel should be adapted with a gas injector that introduces the gas directed by an external controller. Within the injection screw (Figure 4), the foaming agent incorporates the plastic mixture uniformly. The mixture of the thermoplastic polymer with a suitable foaming agent, whether chemical or physical, is then injected into the closed mold, where expansion occurs due to the release of pressure, allowing the foaming agent to expand. After this, solidification occurs, and the molded component is ejected from the mold [77].

Some examples in literature highlight the advantages of FIM for b-BTPs. Behera et al. [78] produced PLA/PBAT foams using supercritical CO₂ combined with carbon nanotubes and carbon black. The resulting microcellular foams exhibited uniform cell structures and improved mechanical properties, demonstrating the feasibility of FIM for b-BTPs in packaging applications. Similarly, Xu et al. [72] produced lightweight PBS foams using foam injection molding. The resulting foams exhibited highly oriented cellular structures that transformed circular cells into tubular shapes, effectively mitigating crack propagation. At a mold opening distance of 0.4 mm, the foams achieved fracture elongation of 486%, tensile toughness of 4.586 MJcm⁻³, and impact strength of 12.73 kJ·m⁻², improvements of 98%, 53%, and 29% over unfoamed PBS, respectively. Increasing the mold opening reduced relative density and mechanical properties, although specific impact strength remained higher than unfoamed PBS. These results demonstrate that FIM can significantly enhance the mechanical performance of PBS foams.

FIGURE 4 | Foam injection molding process. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/app.70436)]

These examples support that FIM for PLA and PBS is already at a relatively high TRL (7–8), highlighting its industrial readiness.

4.2 | Foam Extrusion

Although FIM is widely used, the production of foamed parts with b-bTPs is not limited to this method. Foam extrusion is another prominent technology, in which the polymer melt is combined with a foaming agent inside an extruder. As the mixture exits the die, the abrupt pressure drop induces expansion, creating a continuous cellular structure. This process is suitable for manufacturing foamed sheets, profiles, and tubes commonly used in insulation and lightweight packaging applications [79]. Foam extrusion also allows better control over thickness, density, and surface finish, which are important for applications requiring precise thermal or mechanical performance.

Matuana et al. [80] demonstrated that controlling temperature and pressure in PLA extrusion foams allowed them to achieve densities of $\sim 10^9$ cells/cm³ and average cell diameters of ~ 10 μ m, highlighting the potential of extrusion for high-performance foamed b-bTPs products. This technology is widely used for the production of sheets and profiles from bio-based polymers such as PLA [81]. Industrially, PLA extrusion foams are considered at TRL 6–7, reflecting maturity for scalable production while still allowing further optimization for specialized applications.

4.3 | 3D Printing and Additive Manufacturing

Additive manufacturing enables foamed b-bTPs components with complex geometries and controlled porosity. This approach provides opportunities for customized lightweight designs, functional grading, and integration of multiple materials, expanding the application range of b-bTPs beyond traditional molding processes.

Sun et al. [82] reported foamed PLA scaffolds for biomedical applications, where controlled porosity improved cell proliferation and nutrient transport. Despite the lower TRL (4–5), these studies illustrate the experimental potential of foamed 3D printing for high-value, customized applications where traditional FIM or extrusion may be limited. This method is particularly

relevant for biopolymers derived from microorganisms or algae, where small-scale, high-precision parts are required.

4.4 | Compression and Injection-Compression Molding

Compression molding with foaming is employed for larger or more complex parts. In this method, a foamable compound is placed into an open mold, which is then closed and heated. The heat activates the foaming agent while the pressure shapes the component. Injection-compression molding is a hybrid process where the material is partially injected into a slightly open mold, which is subsequently compressed. This allows for controlled expansion, improving dimensional accuracy and internal cell uniformity [83]. These processes are considered at TRL 6–7 for b-bTPs, reflecting pilot-scale or semi-industrial readiness. Such methods are particularly advantageous when conventional FIM cannot provide sufficient control over foam density or internal structure.

Together, these different foaming technologies broaden the potential uses of b-bTPs, providing solutions customized for various product shapes, mechanical needs, and sustainability aims. For this technology, Zhang et al. [84] applied compression molding with supercritical CO₂ to thermoplastic polyurethane foams, achieving improved cell morphology and mechanical properties, demonstrating applicability to structurally demanding parts. These methods are particularly advantageous when conventional FIM does not provide sufficient control over foam density or internal cell uniformity.

Overall, these foaming technologies demonstrate the versatility of b-bTPs in lightweight and functional applications. By linking polymer origin, feedstock characteristics, and TRL, it is evident that mature processes like FIM and foam extrusion are industrially feasible, while emerging techniques such as foamed 3D printing are still at experimental stages (TRL 4–5), and compression- and injection-compression molding have reached pilot- to semi-industrial scale (TRL 6–7). Literature examples substantiate both the feasibility and advantages of these technologies, reinforcing their potential contribution to sustainable material solutions. Specific Energy consumption (SEC), which depends on machine utilization, efficiency, production rate, and polymer

properties, is summarized in Table 2. In the absence of precise data for foamed b-bTPs, it is reported as indicative values for conventional technologies. Although SEC values are derived mainly from conventional polymers, they provide a realistic order-of-magnitude comparison and highlight relative differences between processing routes, which remains valid for bio-based thermoplastics.

5 | Recyclability of b-bTPs Foam Parts

The recyclability of b-bTPs is a crucial aspect in assessing their sustainability and environmental impact. While b-bTPs offer significant advantages in terms of biodegradability and weight reduction, the ability to recycle these materials is essential for closing the life cycle of products and minimizing waste. This section discusses the recyclability of b-bTPs foam parts, the recycling methods available, and the associated challenges.

5.1 | Recyclability of b-bTPs

Bio-based thermoplastics (b-bTPs), such as PLA, PHA, PBS, and others, can be recycled mechanically and chemically. Although often considered biodegradable, many of these materials degrade only under controlled industrial composting, making recycling strategies crucial to reduce environmental impact. The cellular structure of b-bTPs foams, however, adds complexity to the recycling process.

Thermoplastics, widely used in various industries for their versatility and durability, have become a significant contributor to environmental issues when not properly managed [88]. The recycling of thermoplastics plays a pivotal role in addressing the global challenges of plastic waste pollution and resource depletion [89, 90]. Recycling offers a sustainable solution to mitigate these concerns by diverting plastics from landfills, reducing the consumption of virgin resources, and curbing the negative environmental impacts associated with their production. This practice not only conserves valuable materials but also promotes a more circular economy, where thermoplastics can be repurposed, reused, and remanufactured to create new products, thus minimizing the environmental footprint of this ubiquitous material [91–93].

Although degradation of the material may occur during the reprocessing of thermoplastics, the result of such degradation reactions is a significant drop in molecular weight, which leads to the failing of intrinsic viscosity, melt strength, and melt processability, ultimately resulting in poor performance characteristics and a reduced quality of the final product [89, 92, 94].

Major types of recycling processes associated with thermoplastics include mechanical recycling, chemical recycling, and thermal recycling (Figure 5) [89, 90, 94]. Mechanical recycling involves the collection, sorting, cleaning, and reprocessing of thermoplastics into new products, preserving their original properties as much as possible. Chemical recycling focuses on breaking down thermoplastic polymers into their constituent monomers or smaller chemical compounds, allowing for the

TABLE 2 | Comparison of foamed b-bTPs processing technologies.

Processing method	SEC (kWh/kg)	Industrial limitations	Remarks	References
Foam Injection Molding (FIM)	≈0.9–3.1 ^a	Requires mold design and limited to mold-compatible geometries	High TRL (7–8); good mechanical performance; suitable for complex 3D shapes	[72, 74–78, 85, 86]
Foam Extrusion	≈0.4–1.5 ^a	Mainly sheets, tubes, profiles; thickness control limited	Scalable; fine cellular structures; TRL 6–7	[75, 79–81, 85, 86]
Additive Manufacturing	23.1–346 ^b	Limited scalability; small parts	Complex geometries; TRL 4–5; customized high-value applications	[73, 82, 87]
Injection-Compression Molding	3.1–3.2 ^a	Pilot-scale only; requires foamable compound	Controlled expansion; TRL 6–7; good for large or complex parts	[83, 84, 86]

^aSEC value reported is for conventional technology.

^bFDM: Fused Deposition Modeling, a type of additive manufacturing for small-scale, customized parts. SEC includes filament production and layer-by-layer deposition.

FIGURE 5 | Flowchart of the life cycle of thermoplastics, including the stages of production, application, end-of-life, and valorization routes. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/app.70436)]

creation of new materials with minimal loss in quality. Thermal recycling, on the other hand, employs heat to melt and reform thermoplastics into different shapes or products, offering an effective method for repurposing these materials while managing their end-of-life disposal. The synergy among these recycling approaches is crucial in realizing the full potential of thermoplastic recycling, supporting sustainable practices, and contributing to a cleaner and more environmentally responsible future.

5.2 | Types of Recycling

5.2.1 | Mechanical Recycling

The mechanical recycling of thermoplastics stands out as a pivotal method in the field of plastic recycling. This approach involves a series of physical processes, including collection, sorting, cleaning, and reprocessing thermoplastic materials, ultimately transforming them into new products while preserving their chemical structure. Complementing these processes are various strategies aimed at optimizing mechanical recycling [95].

Compatibilizers play a crucial role in this optimization by enhancing the compatibility of different polymers within

blends. This compatibility improvement facilitates successful mechanical recycling by mitigating issues related to phase separation and promoting homogeneity among the recycled materials.

Moreover, impact modifiers contribute significantly to the efficacy of mechanical recycling by enhancing the toughness and impact resistance of recycled thermoplastics. This enhancement is particularly vital within mechanical recycling processes, where the durability of the resulting products is paramount. In addition, the incorporation of fillers and reinforcements offers a viable approach to augmenting the mechanical properties of recycled thermoplastics. By enhancing strength, stiffness, and dimensional stability, fillers and reinforcements render recycled materials more suitable for mechanical recycling applications, thereby expanding the scope of materials suitable to this process.

Furthermore, plasticizers can be employed in certain cases to improve the flexibility and processability of recycled thermoplastics, thereby aiding mechanical recycling operations. This improvement in flow characteristics and ductility facilitates the processing of recycled materials, contributing to the efficiency of mechanical recycling processes.

Mechanical recycling not only helps divert plastic waste from landfills, but also conserves resources and reduces the environmental impact of plastic production [96]. However, to address the challenges associated with material degradation and contamination, it is essential to complement mechanical recycling with other recycling methods, such as chemical recycling, and to implement robust quality control measures. By adopting a multifaceted approach, the efficacy and sustainability of plastic recycling can be maximized, paving the way for a more environmentally responsible future. Among the challenges, mechanical recycling can enhance a variable density of the material, affecting shredding and reprocessing, and can also degrade its mechanical properties, thereby requiring the addition of additives and/or the combination with virgin polymers [97].

5.2.2 | Chemical Recycling

Chemical recycling of thermoplastic, also known as “advanced recycling” or “molecular recycling,” is a process that involves breaking down thermoplastic polymers into their constituent monomers or smaller chemical compounds through chemical processes [98]. Unlike mechanical recycling, which mainly involves melting and reshaping thermoplastics without altering their chemical structure, chemical recycling focuses on depolymerizing or converting thermoplastic materials back into their original building blocks for later reuse.

Certain chemical additives can be used to facilitate the chemical recycling of thermoplastics, such as those that aid in depolymerization or pyrolysis processes [99, 100]. These additives play a crucial role in accelerating the breakdown of thermoplastic polymers into monomers or smaller compounds, thus enabling efficient recycling.

Chain extenders are another category of additives that can enhance the suitability of thermoplastics for chemical recycling methods [101, 102]. By increasing the molecular weight of thermoplastics, chain extenders contribute to improving the efficiency of depolymerization processes, ultimately leading to better recycling outcomes.

In chemical recycling applications that involve controlled degradation, environmentally friendly flame retardants can be incorporated into thermoplastics to facilitate the recycling process [103, 104]. These flame retardants not only provide fire resistance but also support the controlled degradation of thermoplastic polymers, ensuring that the recycling process is effective and environmentally sustainable.

Additionally, biodegradable additives can be introduced into thermoplastics to aid in environmentally friendly degradation during chemical recycling approaches [105]. These additives promote the breakdown of thermoplastic materials into biodegradable components, further enhancing the eco-friendliness of the recycling process and reducing environmental impact.

In summary, chemical recycling of thermoplastics offers a promising solution for sustainable waste management by effectively breaking down thermoplastic polymers into their original building blocks for reuse. Through the incorporation of various

chemical additives, such as depolymerization aids, chain extenders, environmentally friendly flame retardants, and biodegradable additives, the efficiency and environmental friendliness of chemical recycling methods can be significantly enhanced, contributing to a more circular and sustainable plastics economy.

5.2.3 | Thermal Recycling

Thermal recycling of thermoplastic is a recycling method that involves the use of heat to melt and reprocess thermoplastic materials into new products [106]. This process takes advantage of the thermoplastic property that enables them to repeatedly soften and solidify when subjected to specific temperature ranges, making them suitable for thermal recycling.

There are several types of additives used to minimize degradation or stabilize the polymeric composition during this process. For instance, heat stabilizers play a crucial role in maintaining the integrity of plastics during recycling procedures that involve high temperatures. By preventing thermal degradation, these stabilizers contribute to the preservation of the properties and quality of the material throughout the recycling process.

UV stabilizers offer protection against the detrimental effects of UV radiation on thermoplastics, particularly important during thermal recycling processes where exposure to sunlight may occur. By shielding the material from UV-induced degradation, these additives help prolong the lifespan and performance of recycled plastics.

Antioxidants serve to inhibit the oxidative degradation of thermoplastics when subjected to heat, ensuring the stability of the material during thermal recycling. By neutralizing harmful oxidative processes, antioxidants help maintain the structural integrity and properties of recycled plastics, contributing to their usability and longevity [107].

Thermal recycling is one of the most common and economically viable methods for recycling thermoplastics, and it plays a significant role in diverting plastic waste from landfills and reducing the environmental impact of plastic production. However, it is essential to complement thermal recycling with other recycling methods, such as mechanical recycling, to address the challenges associated with material degradation and contamination.

5.3 | How to Assess

Assessing the recyclability of a thermoplastic polymer involves a series of protocols and tests to evaluate how effectively a material can be recycled, as well as its potential impacts on the recycling process and the quality of the recycled material [108, 109]. These protocols typically encompass various aspects of the polymer's physical properties, chemical composition, and behavior during recycling. For instance, the accurate identification and sorting of materials, guided by standardized systems such as the Resin Identification Code (RIC) or ASTM D7611, is a crucial initial step as it ensures that only compatible materials are grouped together for recycling—thereby establishing a reliable foundation for the process ahead. Once sorted, various evaluations are

conducted to determine the condition and suitability of the materials. The Melt Flow Index (MFI) provides key insights into the flow characteristics of polymer melts under standardized conditions, a crucial factor influencing processability during recycling. Meanwhile, techniques such as thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) offer valuable data on the thermal stability of polymers, guiding decisions regarding optimal temperature ranges for recycling.

Mechanical properties, such as tensile strength and impact resistance, undergo rigorous evaluation before and after recycling to understand how the process affects the material performance. Furthermore, chemical analysis, such as gas chromatography–mass spectrometry (GC–MS), delves deep into the composition of recycled materials, identifying additives, contaminants, and degradation products to ensure compliance with quality standards.

Purity assessments are of paramount importance, scrutinizing impurity levels to mitigate the risk of contamination and to preserve the integrity of recycled products. Visual inspections and colorimetry analyses monitor any changes in appearance or coloration induced by recycling, ensuring the preservation of aesthetic qualities.

Analytical techniques such as gel permeation chromatography (GPC) and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) provide in-depth insights into molecular alterations in chemical structure following recycling. These analyses inform decisions on material integrity and processing behavior, driving continuous improvement in recycling processes.

Comparative analyses of products manufactured from recycled materials against their virgin counterparts provide invaluable feedback on quality and performance, guiding iterative refinements. Additionally, life cycle assessments (LCAs) offer a holistic view of the environmental impact of recycling processes, guiding efforts toward sustainability and responsible resource management.

Evaluation of polymer compatibility with various recycling methods ensures efficient processing and optimal resource utilization. Finally, adherence to regulatory requirements and standards is non-negotiable, ensuring the safety, health, and environmental impact of recycled materials meet stringent criteria, promoting responsible stewardship of resources for a sustainable future. The key material properties and corresponding standard test methods used to assess degradation and recyclability are summarized in Table 3.

The specific protocols and tests employed may vary depending on the type of thermoplastic polymer, the intended recycling method, and the goals of the assessment. These assessments are critical for understanding the recyclability of thermoplastic materials and optimizing recycling processes to minimize waste and environmental impact.

5.4 | Major Challenges

The effective recycling of thermoplastics represents a vital aspect of sustainable materials management. However, despite

TABLE 3 | Critical material properties to address degradation.

Property	Units	Test method(s)
Density	g/cm ³	ASTM D792/ ISO 1183
Melting temperature	°C	ASTM C518-D3418
Crystallization temperature	°C	ASTM C518-D3418
Degradation temperature	°C	ASTM E1131/ ISO 11358
Heat deflection temperature	°C	ASTM D648/ISO 75
Melt flow index	g/10 min	ASTM D1238/ ISO 1133
Tensile strength	MPa	ASTM D638/ISO 527
Impact resistance	J/m ²	ASTM D256-E23/ ISO 148-180
% Volatiles by Vol.	%	ASTM D1203/ ISO 4589
Ash content	%	ASTM D5630/ ISO 3451

advances in recycling technologies and growing environmental awareness, numerous challenges persist, hindering the widespread adoption and effectiveness of thermoplastic recycling initiatives. This section explores the current barriers encountered in thermoplastics recycling efforts—ranging from technical complexities to market-related issues—and explores potential strategies and innovations aimed at overcoming them. These are summarized in Table 4, which outlines the identified obstacles to thermoplastics recycling alongside corresponding solutions. By highlighting these challenges and proposing solutions, we aim to contribute to the ongoing discourse on sustainable materials management and support progress in the field of thermoplastic recycling.

5.5 | Comparative Assessment of End-of-Life Routes for b-BTPs

Among the available recycling strategies, mechanical and chemical recycling represent the two most relevant end-of-life routes for bio-based thermoplastic polymers (b-BTPs), each exhibiting distinct advantages and limitations in terms of energy demand, environmental impact, economic feasibility, and material performance. Currently, mechanical recycling is the most established and widely implemented approach for thermoplastic materials, including bio-based polymers such as PLA, PHA, and PBS. In contrast, chemical recycling is emerging as a promising complementary route, offering higher circularity potential despite its higher energetic and economic requirements. A comparative assessment of mechanical and chemical recycling routes for b-BTPs, including energy demand, emissions, costs, and material performance, is summarized in Table 5, based on literature data. The values reported represent typical ranges derived from literature

TABLE 4 | Major challenges to thermoplastics recyclability.

Challenge	Description	How to overcome	References
Contamination	Occurs when recycled materials are mixed with non-compatible polymers, impurities, or foreign substances. Can negatively affect the quality and properties of recycled materials, making them less desirable for reuse.	Advanced sorting and separation technologies	[110]
Material complexity	Some thermoplastic products are composed of multiple materials or layers, such as laminates used in packaging. Separating these materials for recycling can be technically challenging and economically costly.	Material design for recyclability	[111]
Downcycling	Thermoplastic materials may undergo downcycling, where the recycled product has lower quality or performance compared to the original material. Can reduce the economic incentive to recycle and hinder the development of a closed-loop recycling system.	Circular Economy Initiatives	[112]
Technological challenges	Some thermoplastics may not be easily recyclable using existing technologies, especially when they contain complex additives, fillers, or colorants.	Innovative recycling technologies	[113]
Lack of infrastructure—costs	The availability and accessibility of recycling facilities and infrastructure vary widely by region. Inadequate infrastructure can limit the collection, sorting, and processing of thermoplastic waste.	Financial incentives	[114]
Limited Markets	The market demand for recycled thermoplastic materials can be limited, especially when compared to the demand for virgin materials. Can result in a surplus of recycled materials with limited end-use applications.	Market development	[115]
Quality requirements	Many industries have strict quality requirements for materials, and recycled thermoplastics may not always meet these standards. May hinder the adoption of recycled materials in certain applications.	Quality Assurance and Standards	[116, 117]
Consumer education	Lack of awareness and education among consumers about the importance of recycling and the proper disposal of thermoplastic products can lead to low recycling rates.	Collection and education programs	[118, 119]

(Continues)

TABLE 4 | (Continued)

Challenge	Description	How to overcome	References
Regulatory barriers	Regulatory and legal barriers, such as inconsistent recycling regulations or limited incentives for recycling, may impair recycling efforts.	Regulatory Support	[120, 121]
Thermal degradation	Repeated heating and cooling during recycling processes can cause thermal degradation of thermoplastics. May lead to a reduction in molecular weight and performance, particularly in high-temperature applications.	Smart Compounding and Additive	[122]

and industrial benchmarks for b-BTPs. Actual performance depends on polymer type, energy mix, waste stream quality, and process scale.

Mechanical recycling provides net GHG savings with lower energy demand and cost but is limited in effective cycles due to polymer degradation. Chemical recycling allows higher circularity and virgin-like material quality at higher energy and operational costs, making it currently economically uncompetitive without incentives or large-scale implementation. The break-even point for recycling depends on polymer quality, collection efficiency, and process scale. However, current literature lacks detailed, quantitative LCA data comparing mechanical and chemical recycling of bio-based thermoplastics such as PLA, PBS, or PHA, highlighting a gap in evidence on energy use, emissions, and costs for specific recycling technologies.

6 | Developments b-bTPs

Recent developments in the field of b-bTPs are focused on improving recycling technologies, enhancing material performance, and adopting sustainable processes. These innovations aim not only to promote the use of sustainable materials but also to manage waste efficiently. One promising approach is chemical recycling, which breaks down polymers into their monomers, enabling the production of new high-quality materials. Among the emerging technologies, enzymatic catalysis, pyrolysis, and catalysis using homogeneous and heterogeneous catalysts have shown potential [98, 124].

Pyrolysis involves the thermal decomposition of polymers in an oxygen-free environment, generating a variety of gases and oils that can be used as fuels or chemical feedstocks [125, 126]. Catalysis also plays a key role, with two main types: homogeneous and heterogeneous. Homogeneous catalysts, which are in the same phase/state as the reactants, help to break down polymers into simpler molecules, releasing by-products like water that can be repurposed [107, 127, 128]. For this, metals such as palladium and platinum are often used to promote specific reactions that facilitate the breaking of polymer chains [129, 130]. Heterogeneous catalysis, in which the catalyst is typically a solid and the reactants are in different phases, allows for an easier separation of the catalyst from the reaction product.

This method uses heat, pressure, and hydrogen to convert polymers into gases and oils, which can be processed into clean fuels [131, 132].

Alternatively, enzymatic recycling is gaining ground due to its ability to facilitate cleaner recycling with fewer unwanted by-products. The addition of enzymes that accelerate the breakdown of polymer chains can significantly improve the decomposition rate of b-bTPs [133, 134]. Enzymatic catalysis uses specific enzymes to break down polymer chains, providing a cleaner recycling process with fewer by-products. These specific enzymes are designed to make reactions more susceptible to the action of biotic or abiotic agents.

The degradation of materials can generally be classified as abiotic (heat, radiation, oxygen, humidity, solvents/chemicals). Abiotic degradation is typically the first stage after the end of the plastic's useful life. It involves physical and chemical changes but does not involve any biological process to modify the material's characteristics. Some changes can be seen with the naked eye, such as changes in color, while others require characterization techniques, such as mechanical properties assessment. On the other hand, biotic degradation is caused by the action of microorganisms (bacteria, fungi, algae) that modify and consume the polymer or its monomers, producing low molar mass molecules (acids, aldehydes, and H₂O) and gases (CO₂, CH₄, and N₂) [135], that is, bacteria, fungi, and other living organisms can assimilate these monomers through chemical processes.

Furthermore, oxo-biodegradable additives, which promote the oxidation of plastics, can be used to accelerate degradation [136].

Research is intensifying in the areas of biodegradation and material performance in different anaerobic environments, such as landfills [137]. In situ degradation studies and composting experiments are being conducted to ensure that these materials decompose effectively under various intended use and disposal conditions [138, 139]. However, end-of-life (EoL) processes for these materials present some challenges based on the properties of the bio-based materials and the specific conditions of recycling. Thus, recycling processes are continuously improving to increase the availability and reuse of plastic materials [140].

The incorporation of additives and new formulations is being explored to accelerate the degradation of b-bTPs. The addition of

TABLE 5 | Comparison between mechanical and chemical recycling of b-bTPs.

	Mechanical recycling	Chemical recycling
Recycling principle	This route typically involves collection, sorting, cleaning, grinding, and reprocessing by extrusion or injection molding [95–97]	Depolymerization into monomers or oligomers [98]
Technology maturity	Industrially mature and widely implemented [96]	Pilot to early industrial stage [98–100]
SEC (kWh/kg)	≈0.207 ^a [123]	>0.207 kWh/kg (significantly higher due to depolymerization and purification steps) ^a [123]
GHG emissions (kg CO ₂ eq./kg)	−0.79 kg CO ₂ eq./kg PLA ^a [123]	−0.78 kg CO ₂ eq./kg PLA [123] ^a
Market value of PLA (€/kg)	Post-Industrial Waste: ≈0.25–0.30 €/kg; Post-Consumer Waste: no market value, often subject to a disposal fee (refuse charge) ^a [123]	Post-consumer waste: no market value, often subject to a disposal fee (refuse charge) ^a [123]
Number of effective cycles	Limited (typically 2–3 cycles due to degradation) [95, 97]	Potentially unlimited through monomer recover [98, 101, 102]
Main Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low energy demand; cost-effectiveness; industrial scalability [96] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virgin-like material quality; High circularity potential [98–102]
Main limitations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Polymer degradation; contamination sensitivity; property variability [95, 97] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High energy demand; High cost; limited industrial scale [98–100]

^aThe energy required for fusing and pre-condensation in chemical recycling is similar to mechanical recycling. However, chemical recycling is generally much more expensive than mechanical recycling and virgin PLA production and is not yet economically competitive without incentives or large-scale implementation.

specific compounds to blends such as polylactic acid (PLA) can enhance their biodegradability and mechanical performance in various applications, such as biodegradable food packaging [141–143]. Additionally, using thermal stabilizers in material compositions can help control the decomposition process, facilitating the conversion of these materials into fuels. For example, the addition of essential oils, natural extracts, or nanoparticles has been shown to improve the barrier properties of b-bTPs, making them particularly advantageous for packaging applications [144].

Thus, new materials and compounds are being developed to enhance biopolymer properties like strength and durability, thus expanding their application range. For example, the use of foaming agents can create porous structures that promote biodegradation by allowing moisture and nutrients to penetrate the material more easily, enhancing microbial activity. By adjusting the formulation and application of these agents, it is possible to control the degradation speed of the material to suit specific conditions of use and disposal, making them more easily assimilated by microorganisms [145]. For instance, developing compostable materials designed to disintegrate under both industrial and home composting conditions through the use of additives and polymers that promote rapid fragmentation and nutrient release is particularly beneficial for forming organic compounds and soil fertilizers in the agricultural sector [146].

Laboratory experiments and literature reviews explore various aspects of bioplastics, including production, characterization, application, and biodegradation. These studies highlight, for example, the development of thermoplastic starch blends with nanocomposites.

Table 6 outlines some of these significant advances, including improvements in material performance, sustainability, and functionality through the incorporation of additives and reinforcements.

Furthermore, there is a growing trend toward adopting OF low-energy processes for bioplastic production, aiming to reduce the carbon footprint associated with manufacturing. This involves incorporating renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind, into processing operations, which is crucial for minimizing the environmental impact of bioplastic manufacturing [154]. Thus, as research and development progress, b-bTPs are expected to become more affordable, making it possible to recycle and process them in a way comparable to conventional materials. In situ degradation studies are essential to understand the behavior of b-bTPs under different environmental conditions. Additionally, the establishment of policies and regulations will determine the future of b-bTPs commercialization, as the emergence of sustainable technologies and stricter regulations can accelerate the adoption of b-bTPs solutions. Mechanical and thermal property ranges presented in Table 7 were compiled from technical databases and academic review papers, whereas cost values are indicative and based on average industrial resin prices and market reports. Reported production and consumption figures vary between sources, depending on the polymers considered and the accounting approach employed.

7 | Market and Industry Trends

The packaging industry remains the primary market for bio-based thermoplastics, but emerging applications are

TABLE 6 | Approaches to improve degradation-related properties of b-bTPs.

Objective	Study	Result/conclusions	References
Improving the properties of thermoplastic starch	The addition of plasticizers, reinforcements, and nanofillers (such as montmorillonite and cellulose nanocrystals) were used to overcome limitations such as low mechanical strength and moisture sensitivity.	Studies have shown that these additives increase the mechanical strength, hydrophobicity, and biodegradability of TPS, although they may reduce optical properties such as transparency and luminosity.	[147–149]
Nanocellulose as a reinforcement in biodegradable polymers	In situ polymerization with nanocellulose was used to improve mechanical and printing properties.	Composites with nanocellulose show enhanced mechanical properties such as high tensile strength and extensibility and environmental benefits, making them suitable for a wide range of applications such as packaging and biomedical devices, for example, and wearable therapeutic devices.	[150–152]
Biochar polymer composites	Biochar polymer composites exhibit high thermal stability, high surface area, and electrical conductivity, which makes them a viable alternative to traditional carbonaceous fillers in polymer-based composites.	Biochar, derived from biomass, is used as a sustainable filler in thermoplastic composites, improving thermal stability, mechanical properties, and electrical conductivity.	[153]

expanding their reach. In the biomedical sector, PLA and PHAs are utilized in implants, sutures, and tissue scaffolds due to their biocompatibility. In textiles, bio-PET is increasingly adopted as a sustainable option for fibers and fabrics. In the transport and electronics industries, PBS and bio-based composites are applied in interior components, lightweight panels, and insulation systems, helping to reduce weight and enhance energy efficiency. Regulatory initiatives, such as the European Union's goal of achieving 30%–55% recycled or bio-based content by 2030, are accelerating market adoption. Nonetheless, economic competitiveness continues to rely on technological advancements to reduce production costs and expand feedstock availability [161].

The growth of the bioplastics market has been driven by environmental, economic, and social factors. The industry has significantly invested in researching and developing bioplastics due to the stricter environmental regulations and increasing consumer demand for sustainable products. However, the replacement of synthetic-based with bioplastics in an optimized process is currently a challenge, mainly related to bioplastics properties, such as heat sensitivity, low resistance to shear rates, and narrow processing. Thus, investing in improving the properties of bioplastics, making them competitive in terms of performance and cost, has been a trend in various sectors such as packaging, construction, automotive, electronics, and consumer products [162]. The commercialization of bioplastics and the technological advances in this field are enhancing the properties of bioplastics and reducing costs by combining bioplastics with other materials (blends) through compounding, processing, and additives. Continuous development is essential to overcome the challenges [163] and achieve better mechanical and thermal properties, making them suitable for wider applications.

In 2023, the global bioplastics capacity stood at around 2.18 million metric tons, with production expected to experience

a significant increase to 7.43 million tons by 2028 [164]. This growth has been seen in several market segments, namely in the packaging sector, which represents about 60% of the total plastic production. This is largely due to the favorable properties of bioplastics that help preserve the food quality during transport and shelf life, requiring biodegradable and compostable alternatives [164].

Beyond packaging, bioplastics are being adopted in agriculture (films, mulches, and other products) and in the automotive and electronics industries. The automotive and electronics industries have been incorporating biopolymers into vehicle parts and electronic components to reduce the weight of products. Biopolymer applications, such as door panels, seats, and insulation systems in automotive interiors, lighten products and provide sufficient mechanical strength. Weight reduction is a priority across various industries, including automotive, aerospace, electronics, and packaging, as it helps minimize logistics costs and enhances product performance. In the automotive sector, for example, reducing the weight of vehicles results in lower fuel consumption and lower emissions into the environment [165, 166].

Figure 6 illustrates all market segments where the use of bioplastics becomes an asset, along with some examples.

7.1 | Global Policy Frameworks and Market Distribution of Bio-Based Thermoplastics

The development and market penetration of bio-based thermoplastics are strongly influenced by regional policy environments, industrial structures, and resource availability. In general, regulatory pressure, sustainability targets, and consumer awareness play a key role in shaping demand, while production capacity is largely determined by access to biomass

TABLE 7 | Typical properties of b-bTPs and conventional thermoplastics.

Based content	Material	Tensile strength (MPa)	HDT/deflection temp (°C)	Impact strength (Charpy ISO 179, kJ/m ²)	Approx. cost (€/kg)	Remarks	References
Biobased	PLA	≈21–75	≈55–65	≈2–6	≈3–5	Crystallinity and processing affect properties; amorphous PLA more brittle	[155–160]
	PBS	≈19–35	≈90–110	≈3–6	≈2.7–3.5	Properties vary with copolymer content and molecular weight	[155–159]
	PHA	≈20–40	≈50–100	≈3–10	≈5–12 (higher cost)	PHB is more brittle; copolymers show higher toughness	[155–157, 159, 160]
	bio-PE	≈20–40	≈60–80	≈8–15	≈3–3.5	LDPE biobased lower end; HDPE biobased higher	[140, 155, 156]
Petrobased	PP	≈30–40	≈90–110	≈3–10	≈1–1.6	Homopolymer vs. copolymer affects impact	[157, 159]
	PET	≈55–80	≈75–120	≈5–15	≈1–1.2	Amorphous vs. semicrystalline PET differs in HDT and strength	[140, 157, 159]
	PS	≈24–60	≈85–95	≈8–12	≈1.4–1.8	GPPS brittle; HIPS slightly tougher	[157, 159]

Note: Values are indicative and may vary depending on polymer grade, crystallinity, copolymer composition, and measurement method. Costs are indicative and based on industrial thermoplastics price ranges; actual prices depend on polymer grade, supply chain, volume, and region.

FIGURE 6 | Classification of biopolymer types according to their application domains. [Color figure can be viewed at [wileyonlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

feedstocks, existing polymer infrastructure, and manufacturing scale [167, 168]. The global value chain of bio-based thermoplastics comprises several interconnected stages: (i) raw material supply, including sugars, starches, cellulose, vegetable oils, and agricultural residues used to obtain monomers; (ii) polymer production, where these feedstocks are converted into bio-based thermoplastics such as PLA, PHA, PBS, bio-PET, and bio-PE; (iii) incorporation of modifiers and additives to tailor mechanical, thermal, and processing properties; and (iv) equipment manufacturing and polymer processing, involving extrusion, injection molding, and related technologies for final product fabrication. Regional specialization across these stages contributes to the observed imbalance between production capacity and consumption, reinforcing supply-chain dependencies and influencing technology deployment (Table 8).

Europe is one of the most regulation-driven markets for bio-based thermoplastics, with consumption supported by sustainability-oriented policies and a strong focus on packaging and circular economy solutions. Key frameworks include the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, directives restricting single-use plastics, and European standards such as EN 16785 (bio-based content) and EN 13432 (compostability). These policies have accelerated the adoption of bio-based materials in packaging, food-service products, and automotive interior components [166, 167].

Asia, led by China, is the main production hub, combining large-scale manufacturing, access to biomass feedstocks,

and policy-driven expansion of biodegradable plastics under national plastic pollution control strategies. North America occupies an intermediate position, with production and consumption supported mainly by voluntary certification schemes and technological development, such as those associated with the USDA *BioPreferred Program* and ASTM D6866. South America contributes a smaller but strategic share of global production, largely linked to bio-based polyethylene derived from sugarcane, while Australia and Oceania remain marginal due to limited industrial capacity and market demand [168, 171].

From a market distribution perspective, production capacity and consumption of bio-based thermoplastics remain uneven across regions. Asia leads the industry in terms of installed bio-based polymer capacity as well as market consumption, followed by Europe and North America. South America contributes a smaller share, while Australia/Oceania plays a minimal role. These regional variations are driven by industrial expansion, biomass availability, regulatory frameworks, consumer demand for sustainable products, and ongoing technological development. The values provided are approximate and based on recent industry reports and market analyses, as exact figures may vary depending on the data source [172, 173].

Despite the existence of supportive policy frameworks and growing market demand, the global bio-based thermoplastics sector remains structurally unbalanced. Regions with

TABLE 8 | Regional distribution of bio-based plastics production capacity, consumption and key drivers (2024).

Region	Bio-based production capacity (%)	Consumption (%) (market share)	Main drivers
Asia	≈55–57	≈30–35	Rapid industrial expansion and large installed capacities for PLA and PA; strong manufacturing base and domestic demand for packaging and consumer goods [169, 170].
Europe	≈12–13	≈25–30	Sustainability regulations and circular economy policies; high adoption of bio-based alternatives in packaging and other applications [169, 170].
North America	≈16–19	≈15–20	Established PLA and PTT capacities; technological development and steady adoption in packaging, consumer goods, and automotive [169, 170].
South America	≈11	≈5–10	Biomass availability and emerging production (bio-PE), with growing demand in regional markets [169, 170].
Australia/Oceania	< 1 (≈0.4)	n.a.	Very limited production; no consistent data on market consumption [169].

Note: Values are approximate and based on recent industry reports; actual figures may vary depending on polymer type and data source. For Australia/Oceania, market consumption data are not available.

FIGURE 7 | Short-, medium-, and long-term priorities for research and industrial development of b-BTPs. [Color figure can be viewed at [wiley onlinelibrary.com](https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com)]

strong regulatory pressure and high consumption levels, such as Europe, are not necessarily those with the largest production capacities, which are increasingly concentrated in Asia. This mismatch reinforces global supply-chain dependencies and exposes the sector to risks related to biomass availability, price volatility, and geopolitical or logistical disruptions. Furthermore, the concentration of feedstock sourcing and

polymer production in a limited number of regions raises sustainability concerns, particularly regarding land use, transport-related emissions, and competition with food systems. These structural imbalances underscore the need for region-specific strategies that align policy incentives with industrial capabilities, and for technological solutions that enable feedstock diversification and more decentralized

production. Understanding these regional differences and supply-chain structures is essential for guiding future research directions and industrial development in bio-based thermoplastics [169, 170].

7.2 | Future Research Perspectives and Industrial Outlook

Despite significant advances in bio-based thermoplastics (b-bTTPs), several technical, economic, and sustainability challenges remain. Addressing these challenges is essential to enhance industrial adoption and fully realize the potential of b-bTTPs as sustainable alternatives to conventional plastics. Future research and industrial efforts can be structured according to short-, medium-, and long-term priorities, as summarized in Figure 7. Short-term priorities (1–3 years) focus on improving processability, optimizing blends, and refining processing parameters through pilot-scale testing and tailored additives. Medium-term priorities (3–8 years) include circularity, feedstock diversification, decentralized production, expansion into strategic sectors, and standardized testing and certification, with research targeting recycling routes, alternative biomass sources, and application-specific formulations. Long-term goals (>8 years) aim to establish sustainable industrial ecosystems, develop advanced functional materials, and define global regulations and standards to enable large-scale adoption [32, 174, 175].

Key emerging research hotspots highlight areas where further scientific and technological advances are needed. The development of advanced blends and compatibilizers aims to improve mechanical and thermal performance, but challenges remain in phase compatibility and property stability during processing. Recycling and circularity strategies are gaining attention, yet achieving efficient, economically viable processes that preserve material quality is still difficult. The exploration of alternative feedstocks, including agricultural residues and marine biomass, offers sustainability potential but is limited by availability and variability. Efforts toward decentralized production could reduce transport emissions and enhance supply security, although infrastructure and logistics remain limiting factors. Standardization through testing protocols and certification is essential for industrial adoption but is hindered by inconsistent methodologies. The creation of multifunctional materials, such as smart or self-healing plastics, promises new applications, yet cost and scalability pose barriers. Process intensification and energy efficiency are critical for sustainable industrial implementation, and life cycle assessment and sustainability metrics require more consistent data to guide decision-making [32, 174, 175].

8 | Conclusions

This article reviewed the challenges and recent progress in the use of bio-based thermoplastics (b-bTTPs), exploring their properties and formulations, as well as the technologies for the production of foamed parts and the recycling of these materials. The growing demand for sustainable materials is driving ongoing research into biopolymers such as polylactic acid (PLA), polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA), and thermoplastic starch (TPS), which are key focal points throughout this review.

The compounding of b-bTTPs, through the incorporation of foaming agents, nucleating agents, compatibilizers, and property modifiers, is essential to enhancing their mechanical and thermal performance, thereby supporting their feasibility of industrial applications and the respective introduction of new and innovative solutions in the thermoplastic materials market.

Foamed part production technologies were examined in detail, including foam injection molding (FIM), foam extrusion, 3D printing, and compression/injection–compression molding. Each technology offers specific advantages depending on polymer type, geometry, and application requirements. FIM and foam extrusion of PLA and PBS (TRL 7–8 and 6–7, respectively) demonstrate industrial readiness and scalability, whereas foamed 3D printing of PHAs (TRL 4–5) and compression-based foaming remain at experimental or pilot scales, emphasizing the need for further development before widespread adoption. These technologies enable lightweight, functional, and high-performance components, with literature examples supporting their feasibility and benefits.

Recycling was also portrayed in this review, with due recognition given to its various methods, including thermal, mechanical, and chemical recycling—each with distinct benefits and presenting specific challenges. The main obstacles associated with recycling highlight opportunities to implement strategies that maximize the value of b-bTTPs throughout their life cycle in the value chain. This review documented and discussed several experimental developments at the technological level, indicating a clear trend toward easing the processing of b-bTTPs. These developments not only expand the scope of application, but also contribute to making b-bTTPs more competitive.

Market and industry trends indicate a promising future for b-bTTPs. Emerging applications extend beyond packaging into biomedical, textile, automotive, and electronics sectors, while regulatory initiatives and circular economy principles are accelerating adoption. Collaboration among researchers, producers, and policymakers will be essential to overcome technical barriers, integrate sustainable processing, and enhance market acceptance. The development of new polymers (e.g., PEF, PHUs) and advanced blends, combined with renewable energy integration, further supports the transition toward a more sustainable and circular plastics economy. The global market and policy landscape for b-bTTPs varies regionally, with Europe leading adoption through sustainability regulations and Asia, led by China, dominating production. North America, South America, and Oceania contribute smaller shares, shaped by feedstock availability and industrial structure, highlighting supply-chain dependencies.

Future research and industrial priorities span short- (1–3 years), medium- (3–8 years), and long-term (>8 years) goals, focusing on process optimization, circularity strategies, feedstock diversification, decentralized production, standardization, sustainable industrial ecosystems, and advanced functional materials. Emerging areas such as advanced blends, alternative feedstocks, multifunctional materials, and energy-efficient processing will further support the development of b-bTTPs. The global market and policy landscape for b-bTTPs varies regionally, with Europe leading adoption through sustainability regulations and Asia,

led by China, dominating production. North America, South America, and Oceania contribute smaller shares, shaped by feedstock availability and industrial structure, highlighting supply-chain dependencies. Future research and industrial priorities can be organized into short- (1–3 years), medium- (3–8 years), and long-term (> 8 years) goals. Short-term focuses on process optimization and pilot-scale testing; medium-term includes circularity strategies, feedstock diversification, decentralized production, and standardization; long-term aims at sustainable industrial ecosystems, advanced functional materials, and global regulations. Emerging areas such as advanced blends, alternative feedstocks, multifunctional materials, and energy-efficient processing will further support a sustainable and circular plastics economy. Overall, by combining technological advances, industrial strategies, market insights, and policy frameworks, bio-based thermoplastics are positioned to expand their applications, enhance competitiveness, and accelerate the transition toward a circular plastics economy.

Author Contributions

Catarina Faria: writing – original draft (lead). **Daniel Reis:** writing – original draft (supporting). **Diana Dias:** writing – review and editing (lead). **Renato Reis:** validation (supporting). **Silvia Cruz:** supervision (lead), validation (lead).

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

No new data were generated or analyzed in this study. Data sharing is not applicable to this article.

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